

Stress transmission in a soft electronic skin with viscoelastic properties

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Abstract. Soft skin interfaces enhance haptic interactions. We focus on a soft electronic skin integrating PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride tetrafluoroethylene) piezoelectric polymer transducers. Previous research revealed the PVDF's output signal dependence on grasping speed, suggesting a viscoelastic mechanical behavior that the soft layer could influence, too. Through finite element analysis (FEA), we explore how the viscoelastic properties of the soft protective layer of an electronic skin affect stress transmission to the PVDF piezoelectric transducers below.

Keywords: Soft tactile sensors, Viscoelasticity, PVDF transducers

1 Introduction

The sense of touch is crucial for human interaction with the environment. Insights from human tactile sensing and haptic perception guide the development of artificial haptic systems, aiming to replicate the versatility of human touch. These systems need to manage spatially distributed and time-varying contact information [1],[2]. Advanced sensing solutions, inspired by biomimicry, include soft interfaces with integrated transducers. Here, we present an electronic skin (e-skin) based on PVDF transducers, integrated on a rigid substrate and covered by a soft silicone layer. In a previous study [3], we demonstrated that the grasping speed influenced the output signal of PVDF transducers covered by a soft protective layer. This suggested a viscoelastic behavior that may be mainly attributed to the soft protective layer. Indeed, we neglect the loss component of the PVDF, as it was proved that the imaginary part of the relevant piezoelectric coefficient for the thickness-mode operation was negligible over the explored frequency range [1 Hz - 1 kHz] [4].

In this publication, we investigate through a novel finite element analysis (FEA) how the viscoelastic behavior of the soft cover affects the stress transmission to PVDF transducers placed below.

2 Materials and Methods

The design of our sensing patch (see Fig. 1a) entails a rigid substrate, an array of PVDF piezoelectric polymer transducers (see [5] for the fabrication process),

Fig. 1: (a) Illustrative picture of the sensing patch; (b) block diagram of the whole sensing system.

and a soft silicone layer on top. In this configuration, PVDF transducers directly transform the received pressure (specifically, the average normal stress \bar{T}_3) into an electrical signal, specifically a charge (Q) [6], such that [7]:

$$Q = d_{33}\bar{T}_3\pi r_t^2 \quad (1)$$

where, d_{33} is the piezoelectric coefficient and r_t is the transducer radius.

The total charge Q on the sensor surface is converted into an output voltage signal through an interface electronics based on charge amplifiers [8] (see Fig. 1b).

Fig. 2 shows the Printed Circuit Board (PCB) and the interface electronics design block diagram. The circuit incorporates two primary off-the-shelf components: the BL600 module (Laird Connectivity, US) for Bluetooth connectivity and the DDC232 (Texas Instruments, US) current-input analog-to-digital converter. The PCB is equipped with digital integrated circuits for power management (e.g., voltage regulator) and a USB interface for data transfer (e.g., FTDI232). The design supports up to 32 sensors via two sockets, each with 16 input channels. Both sockets are connected to an offset circuit to adjust the baseline of the bipolar signals generated by the sensors, enabling the DDC232 to process both positive and negative signal polarities. The DDC232 chip includes multiple current-to-voltage integrators and delta-sigma analog-to-digital converters. It is configured for 16-bit resolution and covers the maximum input charge response. The device architecture allows for simultaneous sampling of the 32 input channels with a configurable sampling rate of up to 6 kHz. Data acquired by the DDC232 is transmitted to the BL600 module via UART. The BL600 features an ultra-low-power microcontroller based on an ARM Cortex M0 chip, which reads, processes, and transmits the sensor data. The USB connection powers the PCB and provides a serial interface for data transfer across the system [9]. The interface electronics has been preliminary validated in [8].

In [3] for the first time, a soft protective layer was applied to our PVDF transducer array. A soft interface is beneficial for safety and sensor protection, allowing the soft skin to better conform to surfaces and objects.

Fig. 2: Interface electronics [8].

In the present work, the silicone-based soft skin is made of *dragon skin*, a widely used material in robotics [10]. The Dragon Skin (Dragon Skin 10 Medium, Smooth-On) material is chosen for several reasons. It is easily disposable and involves a straightforward fabrication process, including preparation, pouring, and catalyzation. The material elastic and hyperelastic properties are well-documented, which facilitates FEM simulations and analysis. Furthermore, Dragon Skin offers a softness similar to human skin, making it an ideal choice for this application. Stress-strain curves exhibit significant variability with the indentation velocity [11], suggesting a viscoelastic behavior. In the absence of a proper characterization of such viscoelasticity, we use the viscoelastic characterization of the human skin [12], which has similar mechanical properties. Here, we investigate how this viscoelastic component would affect the transmission of normal stress to the PVDF transducers below. We perform Finite Elements Model (FEM) simulations consisting of indentations at different velocities and forces, employing a rigid indenter acting on the outer skin surface and generating a normal force distribution modelled as Hertzian. We study stress transmission through the soft cover layer and compute the average normal stress \bar{T}_3 on the bottom of such layer (where transducers are located) as a function of force and velocity of the applied stimulus on the outer surface. The e-skin soft layer fills a spatial region shaped like a cylinder, with a diameter d and height h ($= 2 \text{ mm}$), where d significantly exceeds the radii of both the transducer ($r_t = 1 \text{ mm}$) and the indenter ($R = 4 \text{ mm}$). The silicone-based soft layer is modeled both as an elastic material (dragon skin with $E=152 \text{ kPa}$) as introduced in [10] and as viscoelastic, with the stress relaxation parameters of the Prony series $g_1 = 0.148$, $g_2 = 0.252$ (relative moduli - viscoelastic components), $\tau_1 = 2.123$ and $\tau_2 = 9.371$ (relaxation times) [12]. A fixed support is positioned at the

bottom surface of the soft layer, serving as the rigid substrate to prevent any translation and rotation. A preload of 1 N is applied, followed by an increasing displacement. The indentation velocity is varied between 0.1 and 10 mm/s . The software chosen for the simulations is ANSYS Workbench 2019 R3. A 2D axisymmetric configuration is adopted to reduce the computational time, assuming a perfect alignment between the indenter and the transducer. PLANE183 is the element used to mesh the model. CONTA172 and SURF153 are the elements chosen for the frictionless contact between the indenter and the soft layer. The 2D model was meshed in 9587 nodes and 3596 elements. The processor used to perform the simulations was Intel®Core™ i9-9900K, CPU @ 3.60 GHz, with a 32.0 GB RAM. The computational time for a single simulation is 14 minutes. The meshed model is shown in Figure 3. The normal indentation force is aligned with the y axis and it has a negative sign when the indenter is pressed on the e-skin. In the software, the PVDF transducer is not modeled as a piezoelectric material but instead it is represented as a line (a path), as long as the axial radius and axially aligned with the indenter (see Figure 3).

Fig. 3: FEM design showing the chosen mesh.

3 Results

In an indentation experiment, the contact force increases up to a maximum (press phase) and then returns to zero (release phase). Fig. 4a depicts the total deformation of the soft protective layer under indentation. It can be observed that the maximum deformation occurs at the center of the contact area resulting from the indenter touching the soft layer. In Fig. 4b, the contact pressure is plotted at the contact profile, while Fig. 4c highlights the contact state (contact/no contact) between the indenter and the soft protective layer. Lastly, Fig. 4d displays the normal stress T_3 at the transducer level, which is positioned at the bottom of the protective layer. For normal forces, it is evident that the maximum stress at the transducer level coincides with the projection of the indenter

Fig. 4: Example of FEM results on Ansys: the total deformation of the protective layer [m] (a), the contact pressure [Pa] (b), the contact status (c) and the normal stress (namely T_3) at the transducer level [Pa] (d).

axis on the bottom plane. This suggests that if there was another transducer (as in the actual scenario where the e-skin comprises multiple transducers), not aligned with the indenter, it would be capable of detecting the contact happening nearby.

Fig. 5 shows the electronic skin stimulus and the simulated input of the PVDF (\bar{T}_3) over time. The former represents the displacement applied on the skin outer surface, the latter is the result of the stress transmission analysis performed by FEM simulations. The \bar{T}_3 is computed as an average of the normal stress on the path representing the PVDF.

In Fig. 6, the maximum value of the \bar{T}_3 profile calculated through FEM for indentation at fixed force (1 N) and different velocities is plotted, with a dashed line representing the result for a purely elastic material. It can be observed that, as the velocity increases, the maximum value of the \bar{T}_3 profile also increases. At our highest velocities (i.e. 10 mm/s), the result approaches the purely elastic material characterization.

Fig. 5: Stimulus of the electronic skin (displacement) and input of the PVDF (T_3) vs the indentation time.

4 Conclusion and future steps

These results can be regarded as the first step towards interpreting the velocity dependence of sensor outputs. However, it will be necessary to investigate the potential viscoelastic piezoelectric behavior of PVDF transducers at frequencies below 1 Hz, as the employed velocities in this study all correspond to frequencies in that range. Furthermore, the next step will be to characterize the viscoelastic components of the Dragon Skin, to correctly estimate the viscoelastic influence of the soft protective layer on stress transmission through the layer and on the output signals of the e-skin.

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Fig. 6: The maximum value of the \bar{T}_3 profile is plotted as a function of the indentation velocity (viscoelastic characterization). The dashed line represents the elastic characterization.

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